

Path discovering in maze area using mobile robot

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ABSTRACT

Robotic maze pathfinding problems deal with detecting the correct route from the start point to the end-point in a virtual maze environment consisting of walls. Automated robot mobility is a significant feature, which enables a mobile robot to traverse a maze independently, from one position to another, without human intervention. There is a myriad of autonomous industrial mobile robot applications, including the transportation of goods and parts, domestic cleaning, indoor security surveillance, airport baggage couriers, and a plethora of other applications to traverse dangerous locations. This paper proposes a pathfinding mobile robot in a virtual maze based on a combination of a simplified left-hand algorithm and a line-following control algorithm. The mobile robot works in any maze to determine a route from the initial starting point to the end-point. The approach outlined in this paper uses a left-hand algorithm to solve the maze problem and a line-follower control algorithm to enable the robot to move in a straight line through the virtual maze. The algorithm used is less complicated and prevents the robot from falling into infinity loops compared to the traditional wall-follower algorithm.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous movement systems are mobile machines capable of communicating with the environment and performing various tasks without human intervention [1], [2]. In mobile robotics, the robot can be moved from one point to another automatically in a way called autonomous navigation [3]. Despite the massive development in the area of robotics, robots have many difficulties in real environments during navigation because real environments are dynamic, complex, uncertain, and unknown [4].

A maze is a network of trails and borders. A maze is a puzzle in which someone has to discover a way through [5]. Maze-solving algorithms have difficulties dealing with real-world limitations. It is vital to study those limiting factors to correctly design the software for a maze-solving robot [6]. It is easier to program the robot “what”, rather than “how” to do a task [7].

Generally, there are two kinds of maze traversing classifications: 1) a model-based algorithm, whereby the objects are known beforehand; and 2) a sensory information-based or learning algorithm, which recognizes entirely unknown objects. The sensory information-based robot learns its environment by evaluating the data provided by the sensors [8]. There are many kinds of sensors that use in the design of robots such as tactile sensors, visual sensors, and laser sensors.

A robot designed to traverse unknown confined spaces, such as underground tunnels, caves, and pipes, would depend on a limited number of sensors because the robot must be light and small. Typically the robot would sense using small, low power consumption, infrared, cliff, and ultrasonic sensors, as a small, lightweight robot will have a small power source [9], [10]. Maze-solving is the act of discovering away in the maze. Some maze-solving approaches have no prior knowledge of the maze; conversely, in other approaches, an individual can see the complete maze instantly [8], [11].

This work uses Matlab software to create several virtual mazes. The mobile robot utilizes a simplified wall follower left-hand approach to find the correct path from the initial point to the end-point. This proposed algorithm uses only two sensors instead of three, thus decreasing the weight of the robot. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm uses a line follower control algorithm to enable the robot to drive in a straight line through the virtual maze. The organization of the sections of this research paper is as follows: section 2 presents the proposed method for the pathfinding of the mobile robot, section 3 shows the main results of this work in a virtual environment, and the last section presents a summary conclusion of the work.

2. MOTIVATION

The problem of solving a maze is a classic robotic problem discussed for more than three decades. However, it is still a fundamentally significant area of robotic systems [12]. Autonomous maze solving is dependent on the robot's decision-making algorithm. After placing the robot in an unknown environment, the robot executes its decision-making algorithm concerning its sensory inputs to achieve its goals. Many maze-solving algorithms are available such as Lee's algorithm, flood fill algorithm, wall follower - to name just a few [13]. The wall follower algorithm typically defines the end-point target with a specific sign. However, the location of the target is initially unknown to the robot. The wall follower algorithms can be implemented based on the right-hand or left-hand rule [14].

The algorithm defined in this research uses the left-hand rule: the decision tree performs sensory tests from left to right. If the robot cannot first turn left, then it will check the forward direction. In the next step, it will attempt a right turn. If it cannot execute any of those movements, the robot will turn right again, having turned 180 degrees, then return to the last successful turning point [15]. Upon returning to the last successful turning point, the robot will be facing the other way, and it can execute the decision tree from left to right, find a different outcome, or return to the next previous point. Similarly, the right-hand algorithm works in the same way, but its decision tree starts from right to left [16]. The left-hand wall follower algorithm does not need the right side sensor because the robot only senses left and forward walls.

2.1. The motivation of robot kinematic model

The kinematic model is used to find the robot speed in the inertial frame as a function of the speed of wheels and the robot geometric parameters [17]. Assume $pp = [xx yy \theta\theta]^T$ represent the robot posture vector, where x and y represent the robot location, and θ is the angle between the heading direction and the X-coordinate, as shown in Figure 1. The angular velocities ω_L , ω_R control the wheels of the robot. The relationships between the circumferential speeds V_R , V_L and ω_L , ω_R are [18]:

$$V_L = R\omega_L \quad (1)$$

$$V_R = R\omega_R \quad (2)$$

where R represents the radius of the wheels.

These equations can represent a robot, kinematic model:

$$\dot{x} = V \cos(\theta) \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{y} = V \sin(\theta) \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \omega \quad (5)$$

$$V = \frac{V_L + V_R}{2} \quad (6)$$

$$\omega = \frac{V_L - V_R}{D} \quad (7)$$

The relation between the vector of velocities and the posture vector p expressed in the X-Y coordinate has derived as:

$$\dot{p} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\cos(\theta)}{2} & \frac{\cos(\theta)}{2} \\ \frac{\sin(\theta)}{2} & \frac{\sin(\theta)}{2} \\ \frac{1}{D} & -\frac{1}{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_L \\ V_R \end{bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

2.2. The motivation of using left-hand algorithm

The left-hand algorithm works in such a way that the algorithm checks its left-side and front-side to see if there is a wall with turning to the first non-wall side [19]. If the robot cannot execute any of these movements, it has the option to turn right, as illustrated by the flowchart in Figure 2 [20].

A pseudo-code for the wall follower algorithm with the left-hand rule is as follows:

```
# Wall follower, Left – hand Rule
If left is open Then
turn_left
Else If the front is open Then
go_forward
Else turn_around
Loop
```


Figure 1. Kinematics of the mobile robot

Figure 2. Maze-solving flowchart

2.3. The motivation of using line following algorithm

The task of line following is achieved by executing a particular algorithm using two sensors mounted at the bottom of the robot. Pulse-width modulation (PWM) controls the motors' speed and hence, controls the robot's motion and speed of rotation. Three robotic states occur in the following scheme expressed as three output directions: left, right, and forward. Table 1 shows the designing algorithm of line follower control. Figure 3 shows the line follower flowchart. The algorithm gets the data from the two sensors and determines the next motion of the robot.

Table 1. Line follower control algorithm

Statue	Input		Output
	Left sensor	Right sensor	
	0	0	Forward (both motors in the same speed)
	1	0	Increase the speed of right motor
	0	1	Increase the speed of left motor

Figure 3. The flowchart of the line following the algorithm

3. IROBOT CREATE

The iRobot create is a reprogrammable version of the Roomba vacuum cleaner for researchers, educators, and robotics hobbyists. iRobot create is the most popular design platform used to support research [21], [22] and educational activities in mechatronic and robotic areas [23]-[25]. The iRobot creates components, contain light emitting diode (LEDs), serial port, cliff sensors, speakers, infrared (IR) receiver, and two differentially-driven wheels. The iRobot create can be programmed by serial port directly from the computer through an application programming interface (API) command line. Figure 4 shows the structure of iRobot, Figure 4(a) top-view of the robot and Figure 4(b) bottom-view of the robot platform.

Figure 4. The iRobot structure: (a) top-view of the robot and (b) bottom-view of the robot platform

4. MATLAB BASED SIMULATOR FOR IROBOT CREATE

The iRobot create toolbox is a Matlab adapted simulator used for educational purposes. The movements of iRobot create can be simulated and visualized either in autonomous mode or manual mode; the autonomous mode controls the movements of iRobot create by writing a Matlab function program. In contrast, in manual mode, the graphical user interface (GUI) or the keyboard is used to control the movements of the iRobot create [24]. The toolbox contains a main simulator GUI and three GUIs for configuring the settings, replaying the simulation, and creating the map. The Matlab toolbox for the iRobot create (MTIC) toolbox can be used to run the autonomous control program on an actual iRobot [26]. A flowchart of the proposed algorithm is as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The flowchart of the proposal system

Figure 7. The step of exploring a maze using a proposed algorithm (continue)

Figure 7. The step of exploring a maze using a proposed algorithm (continue)

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